

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18474273

Self-Efficacy As Predictors Of Job Involvement Among Guidance Counsellors In Anambra State Public Secondary School

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated self-efficacy as a predictor of job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypothesis tested at 0.05 level significance. The literature was reviewed under the following heading, conceptual, theoretical, empirical studies and summary of literature reviewed. The purpose was to determine the extent to which guidance counsellors' belief in their capabilities (self-efficacy) influences their level of commitment, enthusiasm, and psychological identification with their job roles. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the guidance counsellors comprised of 122 professionals from 267 public secondary schools in Anambra state. The study employed a census sampling method, where the population of 122 professional guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state was used as the sample. Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) developed by Sherier et al (1982) and Job Involvement Scale (JIS) developed by Loadh Ikejner (1965) were adopted as instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. The reliability of the instruments were established using Cronbach Alpha method. The computation yielded co-efficient values of 0.86 for self-efficacy scale and 0.90 for job involvement scale respectively. The researcher administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of three research assistants who were properly briefed on how to administer and retrieve copies of the instruments. Data were analyzed using regression analysis. Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that self-efficacy significantly predict job involvement. Based on the findings, it was recommended that government and school administrators provide continuous professional development and support systems to enhance counselors' self-efficacy and overall job performance. The study contributed to the existing body of knowledge by providing localized data specific in Anambra state, offering insights into how belief in one's professional capability influences the extent of involvement in job roles within public secondary schools.

Keywords: self-efficacy, job involvement, guidance counsellors

INTRODUCTION

Job involvement refers to the extent to which an individual is engaged and invested in their work. It includes factors such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, job engagement and job identification. High job involvement is characterized by strong emotional attachment to the job, high level of motivation, active participation in work-related activities and sense of responsibility and accountability. In today's competitive productivity, every organization faces new challenges as regards to

sustained productivity and creating committed workforce. Every organization has aims or objectives which it sets out to achieve. For organization to achieve their desired goals, they must need the cooperative efforts of persons who form the productive base or workforce. No organization therefore can perform at peak level unless each employee is committed to the organization's objectives. Kanugo (2018), job involvement is a cognitive state of identification with one's job which is characterized by a sense of psychological attachment to the job and a feeling of being fully engaged in the job. These employees join the organization with certain motives which they equally hope to realize while performing their various tasks in the organization. Guidance counsellors in public secondary schools face several challenges that affect their job involvement, including high workloads that leads to burnout, limited resources that hinder effective support, and inadequate administrative backing. Additionally, unclear role definitions create confusion about responsibilities, while a lack of professional development opportunities limits engagement. The emotional strain from handling students personal issues can lead to fatigue, and challenging student behaviours contribute to a stressful work environment. Furthermore, insufficient recognition for their contributions diminishes motivation and commitment to their roles. Addressing these issues is essential for enhancing job involvement and the overall effectiveness of counsellors in supporting students. The problems affecting job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools are quite prevalent. Bengisu (2018), stated that studies and surveys indicate that many counsellors report high level of stress and burnout due to overwhelming workloads and limited resources. Additionally, role ambiguity and lack of support from administration are commonly cited issues. Overall, discussions reveal a strong desire for systemic changes to improve job involvement and support for counsellors, ultimately benefitting students as well. Job involvement, defined as the degree to which an individual identifies with their job and actively participates in it, is crucial in understanding employee behavior. It has been associated with productivity, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Guidance counsellors with high job involvement are more likely to contribute meaningfully to student's development, collaborate with teachers and parents, and pursue professional growth. They also exhibit lower levels of burnout and turnover.

In the Nigerian context, particularly in Anambra State, public secondary schools vary significantly in resources, administrative support and recognition of counsellors' roles. This variability can affect how Counsellors view their profession and how engaged they are with their duties. While some may find fulfillment in their career, others may feel underutilized, undervalued, and demotivated. Understanding what influences this disparity in job involvement is important for school administration and government policy makers. Thus involvement is basically persuaded by the reading of an employee about his person's picture of life, and then by the organizational qualities and job attributes. It is also important that managers of any organization put into consideration the way employees view their job and address the challenges during the recruitment process. The level at which the employee values the job may affect the level of his/her involvement when recruited. Kanugo (2018), stated that job involvement is referred to as psychological identification with a job. He noted that if one has high job involvement, the job becomes part of one's identity and is more likely to cross situational boundaries thereby reducing segmentation of the job role and increasing inter role conflict. Saks(2016), described job involvement as the strict cognitive evaluation of one's job and how it pertains to whom that person is as an individual. He also noted that highly job involved individuals make the job a central part of their personal character. It shows the degree to which an individual is personally involved with his/her job. He further stated that job involvement is one's motivated orientation to having the job in which they are engaged. Job involvement could therefore be said to be the level of commitment to work by an employee. It entails the zeal and enthusiasm with which an employee approaches and does his work. This could be seen in how regular he is found at work and the input made both in time and other resources.

The role of guidance counsellors in achievements of the educational goals in Nigeria, makes his involvement very important. The quality of educational process and its products are unquestionably affected by the guidance counsellors job involvement. It therefore implies that effective job involvement of guidance counsellors is a must for educational improvement which the nation through the Ministry of

Education is working hard to achieve. For effective planning, development and implementation of the public secondary school curriculum, the guidance counsellor must be effectively involved and committed to the job. Apart from the knowledge of the subject matter, the guidance counsellor must trust his or herself in his or her profession for the achievement of the required goals in the education. In light of the situation presented above, job involvement is the reaction to a job arising from what an individual seeks in a job in comparison with the actual outcomes that the job provides to the individual. It is also the pleasurable or positive emotional state of an individual towards his/her job. The researcher defined Job involvement as a crucial psychological factor that influences employee motivation, performance, and overall job satisfaction. This therefore, justifies the need to establish if there is any relationship between career maturity, self efficacy and job involvement of secondary school guidance counsellors in Anambra State.

Self efficacy refers to an individual's belief in ability to perform tasks and achieve goals. It includes factors such as confidence in one's abilities, ability to set and achieve goals, resilience in the face of obstacles, ability to adapt to new situations. High self-efficacy is characterized by strong sense of confidence and competence, ability to take on challenges and risks, resilience in the face of set-backs and failures, ability to adapt to changing situations and environments. It also refers to the perceived ability of an individual to engage in carrying out certain assignments to attain a specific purpose (Bandura, 1977). In the nation's educational institutions, guidance Counsellor's self-efficacy are necessary constructs for the Guidance Counsellor's realisation of the objectives and aims of National policy on Education. They exhibit greater perseverance in the face of obstacles and are more likely to implement innovative approaches in their practice. In a school system faced with diverse student needs and increasing psychological pressures, a counsellor's self-efficacy directly impacts how well they manage their professional responsibilities.

If the Guidance Counsellors believe in their abilities and are as well given incentives (for them to be satisfied), there may be adequate job involvement leading to the actualisation of the broad goals of secondary education. In the same vein, there is need for the practicing Guidance Counsellors to believe in themselves and be provided for. This will likely make them put more effort in their counselling job. Tylor (2022) stated that self-efficacy is significantly related to career exploration and decision-making confidence. It is possible that individuals either have self-efficacy before going into the programme or acquire it during the training (Salas & Cannon-Bowers, 2015). Gibbs (2018) noted that self-efficacy is a powerful predictor of how and whether a Guidance Counsellor will act. He stated that Guidance Counsellor's self-efficacy is the belief that one is capable of exercising control over one's behaviour, thinking and emotion. Effective Guidance Counsellors' believe that they can make a difference in children's lives and they counsel in way that demonstrates their belief. What guidance counsellors' believe about their capabilities is a strong predictor of guidance Counsellor effectiveness.

That is, the confidence of an individual to overcome certain challenges or obstacles related to jobs. It is also the thought or ideas people hold about their job to perform those tasks necessary to achieve a desired outcome. This would imply that the beliefs guidance Counsellors in secondary schools have in their capabilities to do counselling work might affect their level of job involvement (job performance) which is a measure of how well or how badly somebody does his work or task before him. Self-efficacy is also the belief or faith that one is capable of performing in a certain manner to attain a certain set of goals. It is believed that our personalized idea of self-efficacy affects our social interactions in almost every way. Understanding how to foster the development of self-efficacy is vitally important goal for positive psychological developments because it can lead to living a more productive and happy life. The researcher defines self-efficacy as a critical psychological construct influencing motivation, behaviour, and the ability to overcome challenges.

In view of the above definition, self-efficacy is one of the most important aspects of human behaviour which makes a difference in their feeling, thinking and acting. Self-efficacy relates to personal beliefs regarding competencies and abilities. It is a significant trait in an individual, which helps him/her in

accomplishment of his/her goals. Such people are likely to undertake difficult tasks as challenges and are motivated to master them rather than avoid them.

Gender has been shown to be a significant factor in the prevalence and expressions of job involvement. Gender refers to social, cultural, and psychological attributes associated with being masculine, feminine and non-binary identities. It is distinct from sex, which is based on biological characteristics that defines males, female and intersex bodies. Owusu-Ansa et al (2020) defined gender as the socially constructed roles, behaviours, expressions, and identities that a society considers appropriate for individuals based on their assigned sex. Research on gender difference in predicting job involvement has been inconsistent among Guidance counsellors. Nwosu and Okafor (2020) found that female guidance counsellors exhibit higher rates of job involvement than male guidance counsellors. In the same vein, Okoro (2019) indicated that female guidance counsellors are higher in the manifestation of job involvement than male guidance counsellors. On the other hand, Zhu et al (2024) found that male guidance counsellors have more job involvement than female guidance counsellors. However, Lin et al (as cited in Farag, 2023) showed no significant difference between male and female guidance counsellors in the manifestation of job involvement.

Self-efficacy among guidance counsellors is a serious issue because a counsellor with high self-efficacy is more likely to take initiative, remain resilient in challenging situations, and persist in helping students achieve personal and academic success. While there are several international studies on the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of guidance counsellors, there is a gap in literature with regard to the specific context of Nigerian guidance counsellors, particularly those in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Understanding how self-efficacy predicts job involvement in this population is crucial for informing effective job performance, involvement and policy development aimed at promoting guidance counsellors well-being. Therefore the study sought to investigate the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

Statement of the Problem

Job involvement among guidance counsellors has become a grieving concern in public secondary schools. The transition to professional life often exposes guidance counsellors to numerous stressors such as academic pressure, financial stress, social comparison, identity struggles, adjustment challenges, and in some cases separation from family supports systems. These stressors can increase vulnerability to mental health problems including depression and passive thoughts. Given the rising incidence of depression issues, including among guidance counsellors and the critical role self-efficacy may play in prevention, this study sought to examine the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement among Guidance counsellors.

Specifically, the study investigated.

1. Predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools.
2. The predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary school in Anambra state.

Research Question

The study was guided by the following research questions

1. What is the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. What is the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. Self-efficacy would not significantly predict job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

- Self efficacy would not significantly predict job involvement among male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODS

The study adopted correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra state. The population of the study comprised 122 professional guidance counsellors, comprising 57 males and 65 females. The sample of the study was 122 respondents. This consisted of (57 males and 65 females) professional guidance counsellors from public secondary schools in Anambra state. The sample size was drawn using census sampling. This approach was adopted due to the relatively small population on size, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the phenomenon under study. Two instruments used for data collection were Self-Efficacy Scale (SES) developed by Sherer, Maddax, Mercadenife, Prentice-Dunn, Jacoba and Roggers (1982) and Job involvement scale developed by Loadhi and Kejner (1965). The face validity of the instruments was determined by three experts. The experts were requested to examine instruments content coverage, relevance of the items to the topic, clarify of the language used and suitability in converging the variables of the study. Their comments, suggestions and recommendations were used to modify the items before the final production of the instruments. The reliability of the instruments were established using Cronbach Alpha method. The result gave co-efficient values of 0.86 for self efficacy scale and 0.90 for job involvement scale respectively. The researcher administered the instruments to the respondents with the help of three research assistants. On the spot delivery method for administration and retrieval of the instruments were adopted to ensure high return rate. Simple regression statistics was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Simple regression analysis of self-efficacy on job involvement of guidance counsellors.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	SE of Estimate	Change Statistics	df ₁	df ₂	Sig	F Change
					R ² Change			F Change	
1	0.677 ^a	0.459	0.454	5.365	0.459	99.986	1	118	0.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), self-efficacy.

Result in Table 1 revealed the regression analysis for the amount of variation in job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State that was predicted by self-efficacy. The result revealed that when the responses of respondents on self-efficacy were correlated with job involvement, a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.677 with associated coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.459 were obtained. This coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.459 indicated that 45.9% of variation of job involvement could be predicted by self-efficacy in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: *What is the predictive value of self-efficacy on job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Simple regression analysis of self-efficacy predicting job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	SE of Estimate	Change Statistics	df ₁	df ₂	Sig	F Change
					R ² Change			F Change	
Male									
1	0.678 ^a	0.460	0.449	5.506	0.460	40.862	1	48	0.000
Female									
	0.676 ^a	0.457	0.449	5.414	0.457	57.196	1	68	0.000

- a. predictors: (constant), male self-efficacy.
- b. predictors: (constant), female self-efficacy.

Table 2 displayed the regression analysis for the amount of variation in male and female job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State that could be predicted by male and female self-efficacy. Findings showed that when the responses of respondents on male self-efficacy were correlated with male job involvement, a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.678 with associated coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.460 were obtained. This coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.460 revealed that 46.0% variation in male job involvement could be predicted by male self-efficacy. Invariably, when the responses of respondents on female self-efficacy were correlated with female job involvement, a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.676 with associated coefficient of determination R² of 0.457 were obtained. This coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.457 deduced that 45.7% variation in female job involvement could be predicted by female self-efficacy.

Hypothesis 1: Self-Efficacy would not significantly predict job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Regression ANOVA test of significance for the variation in job involvement among guidance counsellors that can be predicted by self-efficacy.

Model		Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
1	Regression	2878.856	1	2878.856	99.986	0.000
	Residual	3397.511	118	28.792		
	Total	6276.367	119			

Dependent variable: job involvement

Predictor: (constant), self-efficacy

Table 3 showed that the variation in job involvement among guidance counsellors that was predicted by self-efficacy was significant (F (1, 118)=99.986, p=0.000). The associated p-value of 0.000 when compared with 0.05 level of significance was found to be less than 0.05. Since, 0.000 was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant variation in job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools that was predicted by self-efficacy.

Hypotheses 2: Self-efficacy would not significantly predict job involvement among male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Regression ANOVA test of significance for the variation in job involvement among male and female guidance counsellors that can be predicted by self-efficacy.

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
1	Male					
	Regression	1238.805	1	1238.805	40.862	0.000
	Residual	1455.215	48	30.317		
	Total	2694.020	49			
	Female					
	Regression	1676.902	1	1676.902	57.196	0.000
Residual	1993.669	68	29.319			
Total	3670.571	69				

Dependent variable: male and female job involvement

Predictors: (constant), male and female job self-efficacy

The regression ANOVA test of significance for the variation in job involvement of male and female guidance counsellors that can be predicted by male and female self-efficacy as shown in Table 4 indicated that F-ratio associated with regression was 40.862 for male and p-value of 0.000 while F-ratio associated with regression was 57.196 for female and p-value of 0.000. Since the p-values (0.000 and 0.000) were less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction of male and female job involvement of guidance counsellors by male and female self-efficacy was rejected. Invariably, male and female self-efficacy significantly predicted male and female job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study in Table 1 showed that self-efficacy significantly predicts job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that counsellors who have a strong belief in their ability to perform their professional tasks effectively tend to be more committed, enthusiastic, and involved in their job. The result of the findings shows that most guidance counsellors have high self-efficacy and high job involvement. Banerjee (2016), opined that guidance counsellors are more likely to set challenging goals, persist through obstacles, and engage deeply in problem-solving and student support. They are confident in managing student concerns, planning intervention programmes, and working with school administrators on factors that enhance their connection to their work. This result is consistent with Bandura's social cognitive theory (1997) which posits that individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to be motivated, exert effort, and remain resilient in the face of job stress. In the context of school counselling, this belief in one's ability directly boosts professional functioning and job engagement. The Anambra State school environment which may involve limited resources, large student populations, and complex student needs requires counsellors who are confident and proactive. Those with strong self efficacy will likely embrace these challenges positively, resulting in greater psychological involvement in their roles. In line with the hypothesis tested, it was revealed that self-efficacy would significantly predict job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It has also been reported that high self-efficacy allows people to select challenging settings, explore their environment or create new ones.

This implies that the guidance counsellors are highly committed to their job. Many factors may as well be responsible. These may include job involvement as a result of regular payment of salaries and other incentives, regular supervision by the State Post Primary School Board among others. Furthermore, the test of significance for the variation in job involvement among guidance counsellors that can be predicted by self-efficacy which also align with Olayiwola (2016) posits that guidance counsellors with high self-efficacy will perform better on their job than those with low self-efficacy. Also Adu, Tadu, and Eze (2016) in their study revealed that guidance counsellor's self-efficacy was potent predictor of improving students' academic performance in selected secondary school subjects.

The reason for the high self-efficacy and job commitment observed by the findings of the present study can be attributed to the government commitment in the Anambra State. It can also be attributed to regular in-service training, workshops, seminars and conferences organized for the guidance counsellors to update their knowledge and skill. These must have added to the guidance counsellors' confidence, competent, and zeal to be committed to their job which of course contributed to the students high performance in education.

The findings of the study in Table 2 showed that male and female self-efficacy significantly predict male and female job involvement among guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State. However, the strength of prediction may vary slightly between genders. For male guidance counsellor, high self-efficacy often translates to strong independence, confidence in handling complex counselling tasks and a higher tendency to engage fully with school programmes and students. Male counsellors with strong self-efficacy are more likely to take initiative and remain resilient in challenging situations. For female guidance counsellors, self-efficacy also significantly predicts job involvement. Women who believe in their ability to perform their duties are more likely to demonstrate patience, empathy and

consistency in counselling services. However, factors such as family responsibilities or societal expectation may sometimes moderate their full engagement, even when self-efficacy is high. The findings align with Bandura's social cognitive theory, which emphasizes that individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to be productive, committed and persistent in their roles regardless of gender. This is in line with Khurshid, Quasmi and Ashraf, (2013) who found that self-efficacy has positive relationship with guidance counsellor's self-efficacy beliefs and job performance. The result of the null hypothesis indicated that self-efficacy would significantly predict job involvement among male and female guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated self-efficacy as a predictor of job involvement among guidance counsellors in Anambra state public secondary schools. Based on the findings, the study concluded that self-efficacy predict job involvement of guidance counsellors in public secondary schools in Anambra state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. The school administrators should prioritize career development & self-efficacy programmes for guidance counsellors. This would help the guidance counsellors to imbibe the quality knowledge and awareness of their self-efficacy in their job involvement.
2. Guidance counsellors should engage in continuous professional development to enable them update their knowledge and to keep on with the modern global trends to improve the academic achievement of the students.
3. There is a need for the government to provide resources for continuous professional development of the guidance counsellors to help them improve their efficiency in their profession.

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